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Cirrus Light: Ambiguity and clarity in the music of Jonathan Harvey

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Abstract

Cirrus Light is a short composition for solo Bb clarinet, composed during the last year of the composer's life. It is part of the limited group of compositions for solo instrument (without electronics) written by the composer during his lifetime.

Harvey's works, as a whole, are characterized by presenting a wide variety of compositional techniques intrinsically linked to his aesthetic, focused on spirituality. Several reflections are present in the literature relating to the relationship between his compositional techniques (Spectralism, Harmony/Timbre dualism, Serialism, Symmetrical Harmonic Fields, Melodic Chains) and Spirituality. The focal point of his compositional practice, however, is the search for ambiguity and this is nothing more than the tool to express the spiritual content of his music: "... the most important property of spiritual music, or even good music, is that it is ambiguous, or that it is perceived as ambiguous".

The aim of this study is to reveal the topological structure of *Cirrus Light*, illustrating its construction and highlighting the compositional ambiguities that run through the entire work. The present work uses several methodologies considered suitable for the purpose of the analysis. These include the principles of Gestalt perception, the analytical methods of Leonard Meyer, Dante Grela, and Francisco Kropfl, Pitch Class Set analysis and phenomenological and psychological

approaches.

It is hoped that this work will shed light on this work and ignite interest in the works of Harvey's last years, a crucial figure of the second half of the twentieth century.

Keywords Ambiguity, Musical Analysis, Compositional techniques, Analytical Techniques, Segmentation.

1. Introduction

Jonathan Harvey's *Cirrus Light* is a short composition for solo B-flat clarinet, written during the last year of the composer's life. It belongs to the small group of works for solo instrument (without electronics) that he composed. Harvey's entire work is characterized by the adoption of a variety of compositional techniques closely connected to an aesthetic deeply rooted in spirituality: "Harvey has always considered spirituality to be central to music experience in general and to the act of composition in particular..."¹

Spirituality constitutes the philosophical and existential foundation of his musical language, which finds expression through the so-called spectral thinking: "Indeed, the fascination of spectral thinking is that it can easily turn into melodic thinking: there is a large borderland of ambiguity to exploit. It is not a question for me of forsaking harmony and regarding everything as timbre, rather that harmony can be subsumed into timbre. Intervallicism can come in and out of spectralism, and it is in the ambiguity that much of the richness lies"². Spectralism thus becomes an instrument that makes it

¹ Candida Felici, "Spectral thinking as spiritual search ...und electronics ist auch dabei: Jonathan Harvey's Tombeau de Messiaen, String Quartet No. 4 and Speakings", *Rivista Nuove Musiche* 3, Pisa University Press (2017): 120.

² Jonathan Harvey, "Spectralism", *Contemporary Music Review* 19, Part3, Overseas Publishers Association (2001): 13

possible to move between harmony and timbre³ in a continuous play of *shifting identities*:

“They are all playing with the identity given to objects by virtue of their having a timbre... The ‘timbral experience’ is fundamentally one of shifting identities. It occurs when we mistake, however momentarily, one thing for another”⁴.

It is precisely this *large borderland of ambiguity* that constitutes one of the structural constants in Harvey’s music, despite his use of different techniques ranging from serialism to Symmetrical Harmonic Fields, from Melodic Chains⁵ to spectral thinking⁶. In all of these, ambiguity emerges as a central compositional parameter: the privileged tool through which the spiritual content of his music is expressed.

The triad Spirituality – Spectralism – Ambiguity summarizes a large part of the essence of his musical thought. In particular, in the essay *Spiritual Music: ‘Positive’ Negative Theology?*⁷, Harvey clearly states: “But what one can say is that the most important property of spiritual music, or even perhaps of good music, is that it is ambiguous, or that it is perceived as ambiguous. One could also say that only ambiguous music is good; unambiguous music is banal music, or chaotic music”. In this essay Harvey also underlines the historical importance of ambiguity in music, citing concrete technical examples:

“There can be an accelerating harmonic rhythm and a slowing melodic ornamentation simultaneously and one can experience the wonderful sensation that both faster and slower are occurring in one and the same thing. All these ambiguities make for the ‘high points’ of musical experience”.

The present study aims to investigate, through perceptual and structural analysis, the ambiguities inherent in *Cirrus Light*, a piece that presents itself, at first hearing, as clearly segmented and well defined, yet reveals, at a deeper level, a dense network of ambiguities and continuities.

Concerning *Cirrus Light*, Harvey writes:

“The starting point for *Cirrus Light* was the long hours sitting in my wheelchair gazing at the summer sky. The cirrus clouds, which are so high, well-formed and slow changing, were often illuminated by a beautiful light. The clarinet searches the sky for them”⁸.

Cirrus Light was composed in 2012, during the last year of

Harvey’s life. Afflicted by Neural Motor Disease, the composer was assisted by Edmund Finnis for this piece and *Fanfare*, and by Ed Hughes for *Plainsongs for Peace and Light*. The *shifting identities* evoked by Harvey imply an ontological continuity among the different dimensions of sound. The phenomenologically perceived boundaries between parameters such as harmony and timbre, pitch and duration, prove to be perceptual thresholds (*limina*) that conceal an underlying continuum.

If, for example, in Messiaen’s *Tombeau* the *continuum* is represented by the harmony/timbre dialectic, in *Cirrus Light* this principle extends to all parameters. The very form of the piece may be understood as a topological space that is not immediately evident at first glance.

The aim of this study is to reveal the topological structure of *Cirrus Light*, illustrating how it is constructed and highlighting the compositional ambiguities that traverse the entire work.

2. Methodology

This study draws on a number of methodologies deemed suitable for the purposes of the analysis. Among these we may mention the principles of Gestalt perception, the analytical methods of Leonard Meyer⁹, Dante Grela¹⁰ and Francisco Kröpfel¹¹, set-theoretical analysis¹², and phenomenological and psychological approaches. The methodologies of Meyer and Kröpfel are based on Gestalt principles of perception. The methodologies of Grela and Kröpfel divide analysis into articulatory, comparative and functional levels¹³, sometimes using similar terminology. In all cases, the macro-form is structured into different architectural levels. A first phenomenological approach to listening to *Cirrus Light* immediately revealed the presence of strongly characterized syntactic units, as well as a frequent recurrence of formal structures. The work appears clearly segmented into perceptible sections, often recognizable even at a first level of listening. However, this apparent clarity is partially obscured by internal syntactic ambiguities. The units follow one another through various mechanisms of formal articulation¹⁴, among which separation and juxtaposition are particularly prominent¹⁵. In order to arrive at a phenomenological reduction, the units will be described and categorized,

³ Marcela Pavia, “Tombeau di Messiaen ovvero il dualismo Armonia/Timbro”, *Rivista Nuove Musiche* 3, Pisa University Press (2017): 83-117.

⁴ Jonathan Harvey, “The mirror of ambiguity”, *The language of electroacoustic music*, London, Simon Emerson (1986): 178-79.

⁵ Juri Seo, “Jonathan Harvey’s String Quartets”, *Rivista Nuove Musiche* 3 (2017)..

⁶ Felici, “Spectral Thinking as Spiritual Search.”

⁷ Jonathan Harvey, “Spiritual Music: ‘Positive’ Negative Theology?,” in *Contemporary Music and Spirituality*, ed. Robert Sholl and Sander van Maas (Farnham: Ashgate, 2016), 1.

⁸ Faber Music, “*Cirrus Light*,” <https://www.fabermusic.com/music/cirrus-light-5550>. Accessed 5 May 2025.

⁹ Leonard B. Meyer and Grosvenor Cooper, *The Rhythmic Structure of Music* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1960).

¹⁰ Dante Grela, “Análisis Musical: una propuesta metodológica”, *Temas y Contracantos*, (Buenos Aires, 1986).

¹¹ Francisco Kropfl, “Pequeños actos de iluminación”, *Revista Lulù* 1 (2009):111.

¹² Allen Forte, *The structure of atonal music*, (New Haven: Yale University Press, 1973).

¹³ Grela, *Análisis musical*. In this essay, Grela defines articulatory analysis as “el examen de la obra desde el punto de vista de su articulación en función del tiempo y también del espacio (si la música analizada así lo requiere); desde la macro a la microforma”.

¹⁴ The term articulation can have different meanings depending on the context and the author. In this case, it refers to the manner in which two units—whether micro or macro-formal, ranging from individual sounds to entire sections—are connected.

¹⁵ Grela, *Análisis musical*.. According to Grela, the manner in which units or sections are connected to one another—including their separation (“...entre la conclusión de una unidad formal y el comienzo de la siguiente, media un silencio de cualquier magnitud”) and juxtaposition (“Dos unidades se suceden sin que exista discontinuidad sonora entre el final de una y el comienzo de la otra: en este caso, el factor articulatorio no deberá ser un silencio”).

reconstructing their temporal trajectory with the aim of identifying any hidden structural relationships. To support the qualitative analysis, quantitative methods will also be applied, in particular with regard to the parameter of pitch. Segmentation was carried out by considering the identity and recurrence of musical figures, understood as clearly distinguishable Gestalt units. Breath marks, rests, long notes with a relaxing function, structural recurrences and agogic discontinuities were also taken into account.

3. Analysis of the formal units

The first two systems of the piece present the two fundamental syntactic units: they constitute both the matrix of the musical material and the poles between which the work unfolds over time. They are distinguished by two different tempo indications (*Tempo I – fast* for the first; *Tempo II – as slow as breath will allow* for the second).

Already at first listening, and visually in the score, the two units appear clearly distinct in terms of musical content, register and temporal behavior. The segmentation suggested by the musical content is reinforced by the caesura that separates the segments: this justifies classifying the articulation as separation. We shall therefore proceed with the analysis of the first two syntactic units, corresponding to the first and second systems of the score.

In the first unit (A) the relationships between duration and pitch are clearly perceptible: what Harvey defines as *intervallicism* and what Francisco Kröpfl describes as *punctual perception*¹⁶, in opposition to a global, timbral apprehension of the event typical of acousmatic listening.

Figure 1. Unit A, first page, opening

Unit A lies in the low register, presents a fast (not numerically specified) tempo and homogeneous rhythmic values (demisemiquavers). The perception of the duration/pitch relationships is confirmed by the recordings available online¹⁷, as will be demonstrated below. Determining the performance speed is fundamental, since it directly affects the possibility of discriminating rhythmic and intervallic relationships. If the performance were too

fast, punctual perception would be compromised in favour of a global timbral perception.

Since there is no metronome indication, the speed varies according to the performer and their technical possibilities. After various attempts using automatic BPM detection algorithms (which produced imprecise results), a manual procedure was adopted: the recordings in WAV format were imported into Logic Pro and compared with transcriptions made in Finale at different tempi (Fig. 2). The comparison showed an average performance tempo of around 50 BPM. At this speed, a demisemiquaver lasts approximately 150 ms, a duration sufficient to ensure a distinct perception of attacks and rhythmic relationships.

Figure 2.

According to Paul Fraisse¹⁸, intervals longer than 100 ms are perceived as discrete events; Justin London¹⁹ confirms that durations of around 150 ms allow for a clear rhythmic perception. Unit A thus lies within the limits of punctual perception.

Intervallic perception is also supported by the spatial proximity of the pitches: according to Gestalt principles, in particular the laws of proximity and good continuation, stimuli that are close in time and space are grouped into perceptual units.

Albert Bregman²⁰ notes that intervals within an octave are generally interpreted as punctual melodic lines, whereas excessively distant intervals tend to be perceived as part of a complex timbral texture.

In *Cirrus Light*, the close spacing of pitches and the isochronous articulation support a clear and distinct perception of intervals, which are not absorbed into the overall timbral quality but retain their melodic identity. Having established the categorical status of this unit, we can now proceed to a detailed rhythmic–melodic analysis.

Unit A

Several architectural levels²¹ can be observed:

¹⁶ Pavia, “Tombeau di Messiaen”.

¹⁷ Jean Jacques Godron, clarinetist, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zge4ZRIP-wA>; Fie Schouten, clarinetist, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KXbj_Ss_O0M

¹⁸ Paul Fraisse, *The Psychology of Time*, trans. Jennifer Leith (New York: Harper & Row, 1963).

¹⁹ Justin London, *Hearing in Time: Psychological Aspects of Musical Meter*, 2nd ed. (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2012).

²⁰ Albert Bregman, *Auditory Scene Analysis: The Perceptual Organization of Sound* (Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 1990).

²¹ Leonard B. Meyer, *Emotion and Meaning in Music* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1956), 88–115.

- a lower level of demisemiquavers (uniform rhythm, equal values);
- a second level determined by the rests.

Figure 3.

A divergence may be observed between the regularity of the durations at the first level and the irregularity of the second. The irregular rests interrupt regularity and create distinct perceptual groups. “An isochronal or equally spaced pulse on one level that uses varied pulse groups creates a pulse on the (slower) multiple level that is non-isochronal.”²²

Divergences between parameters generate ambiguity, and this, according to Harvey, is one of the ways to arouse the listener’s interest and enrich the form, avoiding banalization²³.

The higher formal level (indicated by the brackets) is the one that, from the point of view of segmentation, presents the greatest ambiguities. However, it could be divided as indicated in Figure 1, on the basis of:

- agogics: taking into account the longer rests (dotted semiquaver and caesura);
- possible patterns (2 3 3 2 3 6), where the last 3 of the first group is replaced by 6, so that we are essentially dealing with a varied repetition of the same model;
- rhythmic–melodic intensification given by the increase in the number of elements.

The succession of notes also suggests certain patterns (the numbers refer to chromatic degrees, with 0 = C, 1 = C#, and so forth):

3 2 3 2 4 2 4 7 2 3 6 3 4 7 6 3 4 5

The second group is a repetition of the first with one element added. The third group is a circular permutation of the second with one element added. The fourth group is a retrogression of the first while the sixth group embeds the fifth.

The result of what has been described so far is represented graphically in Figure 5, where the blue dots represent the

notes, the green lines the groups separated by rests, and the blue lines the next architectural level.

Figure 4.

As the figure shows, the highest formal level is binary and asymmetrical, thus counterbalancing the isochronous regularity of the lower level.

From the intervallic point of view, the relationships are perceivable (according to what has been said above regarding *intervallicism*), and the pitch-class sets present (as determined by the previous segmentation) are: 3-1 | 3-7 | 3-2.²⁴

The corresponding interval vectors are 210000, 011010 and 111000. These vectors indicate the presence of the following intervals: minor second, major second, minor third, major third and perfect fourth. The intervals listed above, corresponding to the vectors (and thus to the structural network), do not fully coincide with what actually appears at the surface level, namely the direct intervals. These are perceptually more important than the indirect (network) intervals. In the present case, the direct intervals are: minor second, major second and minor third; consequently, the perceptual outcome is more chromatic than the structural network alone would suggest²⁵. Pitches are not absolute; furthermore, the temporal evolution of the register produces a constant upward curve.

Unit B

Unit B (Fig. 6) presents features that strongly contrast with those of A: it has an extremely slow tempo, indeterminate rhythmic values (the notes last as long as the performer’s breath allows), and unfolds in the high register.

Figure 5. Unit B, first page, second and third systems.

²² Allen Winold, “Rhythm in Twentieth-Century Music,” in *Aspects of Twentieth-Century Music*, ed. Gary Wittlich (Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall, 1975).

²³ The delicate balance between clarity and ambiguity is, moreover, a formal issue inherent in artistic works of every style and period.

²⁴ This classification derives from Allen Forte’s pitch-class set analysis.

²⁵ Marcela Pavia, *La estructura de la música atonal: dos enfoques* (Barcelona: CODEXXI, 1998). According to Kröppf’s methodology, pitch sets (which he calls *micromodes*) are classified into two broad categories:

those organized around the minor second (minor) and those organized around the major second (major). The former are more chromatic than the latter (predominantly diatonic). Even within minor micromodes, different degrees of chromaticity may be established depending on the presence or absence of the major second and other intervals with diatonic characteristics.

The notes, held as long as the performer’s breath allows, are connected by glissandi that mask the attacks, making punctual perception of events difficult.

This unit can be classified as timbral: the glissandi introduce micro-intervals, rendering the pitch parameter continuous rather than discrete. Pitches “slide” around A (for B-flat clarinet) in fluid “waves”, with a variable number of elements (2 3 4 2).

The prolonged and flexible duration of the notes also contributes to blurring rhythmic perception. In this case, segmentation is determined by slurs and very short breath marks. The *ppp* dynamic further helps to conceal the attacks, favoring a global perception of sound.

In its temporal evolution, this unit remains in the high register. The opening of *Cirrus Light* thus presents two opposing units:

Figure 6.

One follows the other, separated by a caesura: adopting the categories proposed by Dante Grela²⁶, the formal articulation may be classified as separation. These units recur throughout the work, alternating with other units. Before considering their temporal evolution, however, we shall analyze the other formal units, which are likewise recurrent. An interesting aspect to observe is that the speed of change of each unit differs.

Unit C

²⁶ Grela, “Análisis musical”.

²⁷ Grela, “Análisis Musical.” The magnitude of articulation is defined as “la extensión temporal de los silencios que separan las unidades”. It would seem obvious that there should be a proportional relationship

Figure 7. Unit C, fourth system, first page

Unit C introduces a strongly characterizing and easily recognizable rhythm, and is marked in the score as *bird like*. The metronome indication (quarter = 72) and the rhythmic values allow a punctual perception of durations. However, the intervals often exceed the octave, leading to a timbral perception of pitch. The unit is therefore hybrid: punctual with respect to rhythm, timbral with respect to pitch. The formal articulation is one of separation, indicated by clear caesuras. This unit, like all the others, is recurrent and often functions as an interpolation. C tends towards stasis: absolute pitches remain constant and internal transformations are minimal.

Figure 8.

A particularly interesting detail, with regard to syntactic ambiguities, emerges in the articulation of this unit: in the third system of the second page, unit C appears immediately before the four-second pause indicated in the score. This pause marks a separation between C and what follows. Moreover, this pause – the longest in the entire piece (we recall that formal separations in *Cirrus Light* are always constituted by caesuras or breath marks) – would seem to indicate a higher-level formal articulation²⁷. However, immediately after the pause C returns, albeit briefly. This is one of the syntactic ambiguities mentioned at the beginning. On this point Grela observes:²⁸ “En muchos casos se suele presentar una independencia entre el nivel morfológico de articulación (extensión temporal relativa de las unidades formales) y lo que podemos llamar el grado o magnitud de la articulación entre unidades”.

This type of independence constitutes, from a perceptual point of view, an ambiguity, and it is precisely what happens in *Cirrus Light*.

between articulation level and magnitude (a higher level would correspond to a greater magnitude)

²⁸ Grela, “Análisis Musical”

Unit D

Figure 9. Unit D, second page, middle of the fourth and fifth systems

The tempo of D is the same as that of F; the rhythmic values would seem to indicate a punctual perception of durations. This perception, however, is obscured by the repetition of notes with masked attacks. Even more important in obscuring punctual perception is the use of *bisbigliando*, that is, alternated fingerings for the same pitches. The alternation of fingerings produces microtonal fluctuations of the same notes. Consequently, unit D can also be considered hybrid.

It is interesting to note that the rhythm of durations at the first architectural level is irregular, whereas regularity is found at the second level (the opposite of what we observed in unit A). Notice how D seems to emerge naturally from B in a kind of morphing (gradual transformation), as though the sound were changing its surface quality (from smooth to rough).

Unit E

Unit E is the most dynamic in terms of change and summarizes the opposition between punctual and timbral that characterizes the entire piece: initially hybrid, it evolves until it becomes timbral.

Figure 10. Unit E, fifth page, fourth system.

The indication *almost toneless* appears only once earlier and refers to a single note (G, at the end of the first system on the third page). Unit E appears in the middle of the last system on the same page, and is therefore a sort of evolution of an element that, from a small point in space, will become the most change-rich material in the entire piece.

Perception of durations is punctual, given the metronome indication. On the other hand, intervals that extend beyond the octave, the timbral quality of the *toneless* notes and the

dynamics contribute to masking intervallic perception. For these reasons, at this initial stage of its temporal evolution, unit E can be considered hybrid. Over the course of its evolution, this classification changes radically.

Figure 11. Unit E, fifth page, fourth system

In this example the durations are very short and uniform; the intervals are almost always greater than an octave in ascending and descending arpeggios that create a perceptual sensation of waves. The radical change that shifts perception from hybrid to timbral manifests itself primarily in the duration parameter

Unit F

Figure 12. Unit F, first page, middle of the third system

Unit F is the most static and, from this point of view, stands in sharp contrast to unit D. Pitches are absolute and describe an ascending arpeggio with intervals within the octave. However, the speed of execution places the unit at the threshold of timbral perception. Indeed, the indicated tempo (crotchet = 72 BPM) yields a duration of approximately 0.09 seconds for the demisemiquaver, placing the durations very close to the threshold of timbral perception.

F often functions as an interpolation (for example, in the third system of the first page) and maintains a unified gestural character. Although its appearances are brief, the gesture remains recognizable thanks to the stability of its parameters. Only the number of elements varies (8 or 10 elements in its six appearances). From what has been said, F tends to have a timbral character.

Figure 13 and 14 summarise what has been discussed so far:

Figure 13.

Unit	Tempo perceptive	Duration	Altezza	Dinamica	Tempo	Modi di attacco	Altro
A Muttering sounds	Punctual, depending on the performance tempo.	Pulsed rhythm Irregular segmentation. Fast rhythmic patterns.	Chromatic field. Intervals within the octave.	ppp	Fast (unspecified)	staccato	
B	Timbral	Free duration notes (as long as breath allows).	Microtonal Field	ppp	Slow (unspecified)	legato	Glisandi microtonali
C Bird like	Hybrid	Irregular rhythm (non-uniform)	Chromatic field. Intervals beyond the octave. Absolute pitches	ff	♩ = 72	Separato	
D	Hybrid	Irregular rhythm (non-uniform at the lower level)	Microtonal Field	ppp	♩ = 72	Legato	Extended techniques Alternate fingerings (timbral trill, bisbigliando)
E	Hybrid first and then Timbral	Irregular rhythm (non-uniform) then uniform.	Chromatic field. Intervals beyond the octave	ppp	♩ = 72	legato	Almost toneless
F	Punctual	Uniform rhythm. Fast rhythmic patterns	Chromatic field. Absolute pitches	ff/ff	♩ = 72	legato	

Figure 14.

The temporal evolution of the units is almost always one-dimensional. The only constant in the change of units is the variation in duration or in the number of elements (an aspect consistent with the aesthetics of contemporary music); for the same reason the pitch classes change, except where absolute pitches are used. The identity of the units is nevertheless preserved through the stability of the remaining parameters.

Figure 14, for example, shows that unit A is dynamic with respect to register while the other parameters remain constant. It is therefore clearly recognizable throughout its course. The other units likewise maintain their “phenotype”.

Segmentation is always clear because discontinuity occurs in all parameters (with the exception of the instances of syntactic ambiguity already mentioned).

Unit B maintains all of its characteristics, modifying only, as already noted, the duration of each presentation and the pitch classes.

Unit C modifies only the number of elements (although it is always very short, it is nevertheless perceptually salient).

Unit D modifies not only the overall duration of each presentation but also the durations of individual sounds, without undermining its perceptual identity.

Unit E, by contrast, radically transforms its identity, although this is achieved solely in the dimension of durations. Figure 12 illustrates this shift from the hybrid to the timbral category.

Determining the punctual/timbral nature of a unit is fundamental for choosing the appropriate type of analysis. Pitch-set classes analysis would, for example, be suitable for punctual units, whereas spectral analysis might be

more appropriate for timbral units.

There are several particularly interesting points that indicate elements of a continuity underlying the surface. This consideration is important because it is directly connected to our final conclusion.

- Fifth system of the first page: at the end of the system, the sustained note turns into a timbral trill (*bisbigliando*), anticipating unit D.
- End of the first system on the third page: the note G, marked *toneless*, is not only a point of articulation, but anticipates the timbral character of unit E.
- Both the four-second pause and this *toneless* long note are unique points that are ambiguous because they do not separate different units but are instead incorporated within the same unit.
- Last system of page 4: the timbral trills that conclude unit B at the end of the last system of the first page reappear; this time the continuity is explicit because they are followed by unit D.

The units on the sixth page are connected in a much more fluid way and begin to lose their characteristics during more or less gradual transformations. Of these, the most relevant is the transformation from A to E (end of the first and second systems). F is followed by a neutral element, an ascending scale, which leads to B.

4. Conclusion

Units A and B can be regarded as opposite poles within which the others are distributed. The units generally evolve confined to one dimension, modifying only one or two parameters at a time and leaving the others unchanged, thus guaranteeing recognizability.

The unfolding of the form through recurrences suggests an underlying atemporality in which identities that appear to be far apart demonstrate an implicit capacity to evolve fluidly into one another.

The temporal succession of units could have been different, for example a gradual transformation (without changing anything in the units as they have been presented) rather than a succession of recurrences. In either case, staticity, recurrences and an implicit fluidity seem to suggest a topological space as a representation of the macro-form.

The underlying continuity in *Cirrus Light* could be represented as a Möbius strip that has been cut into several fragments and then arranged by the composer in a particular sequence.

The clarity of the work is determined by the convergence of structure and surface and by the recognizability of the units. Syntactic ambiguities, the non-linear formal trajectory, the oscillation between punctual and global dimensions of perception, all blur the *limes* separating these two dimensions. From this point of view, the structural and poetic aspects (the light that alters the contours of the cirrus clouds) mirror one another. In this piece, ambiguity concerns all parameters and constitutes,

in our view, a symbol and logical corollary of Harvey's entire oeuvre.

It is to be hoped that the present study may kindle interest in Harvey's late works, since he is a crucial figure of the second half of the twentieth century:

"Although Jonathan Harvey (1939–2012) is recognized as one of the most prominent British composers, his compositions have not received the deserved attention from music scholars".²⁹

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²⁹ Laura Emmery, "Jonathan Harvey's String Trio: The Rustic and the Sacred," *New Sound International Journal of Music* 60 2 (2022): 149. doi:10.5937/newso2260149E

